

Monitoring rice crop and yield estimation with Sentinel-2 data

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Graphical abstract

21 **Abstract**

22 The future success on rice farming will lie in the development of productive, sustainable,
23 and resilient farming systems. Thus, accurate information on crop conditions and grain
24 yield at optimum temporal and spatial scales is crucial for crop management. This study
25 evaluates the potential application of Sentinel-2 (S2) to monitor rice crop in two
26 consecutive seasons (2018 and 2019) in the Ebro Delta growing area. For this purpose,
27 time-series of four different spectral indexes (NDVI, $NDWI_{MF}$, $NDWI_{GAO}$, and BSI)
28 derived from smoothed S2 data at 20 m spatial resolution were generated. Then, the first
29 and second derivative analysis on the temporal profiles of spectral indexes, were used to
30 estimate the main phenological states, rice development phases, management practices, and
31 crop yield from regional to field scale. The combination of NDVI, $NDWI_{GAO}$ and BSI was
32 used to identify significant farming dates (*i.e.* Tillering, Heading Date and Maturity), and
33 field status (*i.e.* hydroperiod). However, $NDWI_{MF}$ was more effective for estimating rice
34 grain yield ($r = - 0.8$). Sentinel-2 demonstrated its strong capability for the development of
35 new strategies for rice monitoring and crop management, by providing information at high
36 spatial and temporal scales.

37

38 **Keywords:** Remote sensing, Agriculture; Time-series; Smoothing; Rice phases; Ebro Delta

39 **1. Introduction**

40 Rice provides food for more than half of the world's population, occupying more than 12 %
41 of the world crop area, providing important ecosystems services such as habitat for fauna,
42 prevention of saline intrusion and soil erosion, subsidence mitigation, and nutrient cycling
43 (Tornos *et al.*, 2015). Timely and accurate information on crop conditions (*e.g.*
44 physiological state, hydroperiod) is crucial for crop management to increase efficiency,
45 productivity, and sustainability (Wan *et al.*, 2020). However, vegetation dynamics and
46 hence rice yield, vary temporally and spatially due to several factors such as differences in
47 soil properties, climatology, and management practices (Casanova, 1998; Bradley *et al.*,
48 2007). With the rapid development of geospatial technology in the last years, acquisition of
49 high-quality spatial and temporal data has become cost effective and efficient. In particular,
50 multispectral satellite remote sensing has proved its usefulness in monitoring rice crop,
51 water regime, and in estimating yield production (Mosleh *et al.*, 2015; Dong and Xiao,
52 2016). Usually, spectral indices (SI) are used as a proxy for vegetation, flooding regime and
53 crop efficiency because they integrate the information of two or more spectral bands which
54 are sensitive to different plant or soil characteristics (*e.g.* plant pigments or water content)
55 (Zeng *et al.*, 2020).

56 The Sentinel-2 (S2) satellite constellation is an Earth observation mission launched by the
57 European Spatial Agency (ESA) under the Copernicus programme to provide accurate,
58 timely and easily accessible information of the land surface, with improved capabilities for
59 vegetation mapping and monitoring, and phenology estimation (reviewed in Misra *et al.*,
60 2020). The S2 senses at 13 different spectral bands (ranging from 443 nm to 2190 nm),
61 including visible (VIS), near infrared (NIR), and shortwave infrared (SWIR), at spatial

62 resolutions of 10 m, 20 m and 60 m (depending on the band), and a revisiting time of 5 to 10
63 days. However, the use of S2 presents some limitations related to time-series development,
64 including noise and data gaps (*e.g.* atmospheric correction errors, decreased reflectance by
65 shadows, cloud presence). In this sense, a common practice is the usage of multi-temporal
66 images composites derived from the combination of best quality pixels from images within
67 a defined period (Sakamoto *et al.*, 2005; Wang *et al.*, 2012; Tornos *et al.*, 2015).
68 Nevertheless, finding noise-free values may be complicated for short periods of time, and
69 increasing the compositing period may lead to the loss of information (Zeng *et al.*, 2020). In
70 some case there is insufficient cloud-free information present in the multi-temporal data to
71 compose a cloud-free image (Schmitt *et al.*, 2019), and it is necessary to smooth data, for
72 instance by filter-based methods or function fitting methods, to fill temporal gaps and
73 minimize the residual noise (Bradley *et al.*, 2007; Geng *et al.*, 2014). After completing the
74 SI time-series, the analysis of vegetation phenology, irrigation regime and crop yield
75 estimation will depend on the ability to characterize intra- and inter-annual dynamics at
76 optimal scales. For rice crop monitoring, it is crucial to differentiate key phenological stages
77 (*e.g.* tillering, heading date, maturity) and management practices (*e.g.* flooding, harvest),
78 both in space and time, particularly at small spatial scales (*i.e.* individual rice fields).
79 The main aim of this study is to assess the capability of Sentinel-2 to monitor rice crop in a
80 Mediterranean growing area. Specific objectives are (i) to generate spatiotemporal time-
81 series of four SI (NDVI, NDWI_{MF}, NDWI_{GAO}, and BSI) for the identification of the main
82 phenological stages and management practices at different scales (from regional to field), (ii)
83 to provide estimates of rice yield, and (iii) to derive easy interpretable information along two
84 consecutive crop seasons (2018 and 2019).

85

86 2. Materials and methods

87 2.1. Study area

88 The Ebro River (NE Iberian Peninsula) is one of the most important tributaries of the
89 Mediterranean Sea, it is 910 km long, has a drainage area of 85,362 km², and a mean
90 annual flow of 426 m³·s⁻¹ (Genua-Olmedo *et al.*, 2016). The Ebro Delta (Fig. 1), with an
91 extension of *ca.* 32,500 ha, contains a number of ecosystems with high ecological value
92 (*e.g.* wetlands, coastal lagoons, and fresh water springs) included in Natura 2000 network
93 of the European Union and protected as Natural Park and UNESCO Biosphere Reserve.
94 The 65 % of the delta area (21,125 ha) is devoted to rice farming (Fig. 1), constituting the
95 main economic activity in the region and providing important ecosystems services. The
96 climate is typically Mediterranean with a mean annual precipitation of about 500 mm,
97 mostly distributed during spring and autumn, and a mean annual temperature of 18 °C with
98 mild winters (mean temperature in January is 9 °C) and hot summers (mean temperature in
99 July is 24 °C).

100 In the Ebro Delta, rice is grown from late April to September and left fallow during the rest
101 of the year (Fig. 2). In the growing season, water management consists of permanent
102 flooding from sowing time (late April-early May) to two weeks before harvest (September),
103 the water layer is *ca.* 5-15 cm deep. During the vegetative and early reproductive stages,
104 short draining periods can occur for either facilitating early crop establishment, or for
105 herbicide and fertilizer applications. After harvest, fields are re-inundated for the
106 incorporation of rice straw into the soil. Thereafter fields are either flooded from October to
107 December (Re-flooding) or left to progressively drain according to farmers' practices. From
108 January to March rice fields are left dry for soil labor operations (harrowing and fertilizer
109 application) and flooded in Mid-April, at the beginning of the next cultivation period

110 (Martínez-Eixarch *et al.*, 2018). The cultivars grown in the Ebro Delta, are japonica-type
111 with medium grain size and a growth of cycle of *ca.* 120 to 140 days from sowing to
112 maturity. In general, the variability of cultivars grown in the area within a year is low, *ca.* 5
113 different rice cultivars cover most of the cultivation area.
114

115
116 **Figure 1.** Location of the Ebro Delta and coverage of rice paddies under study. Fields I and
117 II are used in support of sections 3 and 4.

118

119 2.2. Study design

120 The study was carried out along two consecutive years (2018-2019). Cadastral data of all
121 rice parcels were obtained from the Department of Agriculture, Livestock, fisheries, and
122 food of the regional government (<http://agricultura.gencat.cat>). Four scenarios, considering

123 different spatial scales, were analyzed: Scenario ‘A’ included all rice fields in the Ebro
 124 Delta; Scenario ‘B’ and ‘C’ considered all paddies in the northern and southern hemidelta,
 125 respectively; and in Scenario ‘D’ 67 individual rice fields were analyzed (Fig. 1) for which
 126 field and crop information, including cultivar, soil properties, agricultural practices (*i.e.*
 127 sowing and harvesting dates), and yield ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$), were obtained from the owner. In
 128 Scenario ‘D’, Field I and Field II (Fig. 1) were chosen as example to facilitate results
 129 interpretation. Field I (10.8 ha) is close to the Ebro River (Fig. 1) and seeded with *Mare*
 130 cultivar in both 2018 and 2019. Field II is the largest field in scenario ‘D’ (37.4 ha), *Bomba*
 131 and *Sirio* cultivars were grown in 2018 and 2019, respectively.

132

133
 134 **Figure 2.** Rice farming calendar in the Ebro Delta. Adapted from (Martínez-Eixarch et al.,
 135 2018)

136
 137 **2.3. Satellite data**

138 Google Earth Engine (GEE), a cloud-based platform for long term geospatial analysis
 139 (Gorelick *et al.*, 2017), was used for data access, clouds and clouds shadows detection,
 140 image pre-processing (*i.e.* image subset, mosaicking of tiles and image resampling), and
 141 spectral index calculation. In GEE, image collections of both Sentinel-2 A/B (S2) top of
 142 atmosphere (L1C, TOA) and atmospherically corrected for surface reflectance (L2A, BOA)

143 from 1st of January 2018 to the 31st of December 2019 were used. All images were obtained
144 from the same orbit (051) and tiles (TCF31 and TBF31) to homogenize remote sensing
145 measurements and ensuring the full coverage of the study area. First, all available BOA
146 images within the study period were loaded ($N_{images} = 138$); then, TOA images were
147 selected based on the available BOA dates. TOA images were needed as base of the method
148 used for masking clouds and cloud shadows (adapted from Schmitt *et al.*, 2019). Only the
149 second module of the Schmitt *et al.* (2019) method was used (i.e. image quality score
150 module). This generates a pixels scoring for each independent TOA image and date by
151 combining the probabilities of cloud presence given different assumptions about brightness,
152 moisture, and snow. Cloud masks were derived with a threshold of 0.3 on the pixel score.
153 Then, the cloud masks, in conjunction with the TOA images metadata (sun azimuth and
154 zenith) and a range of possible cloud heights (from 200 m to 10000 m) were used to
155 generate shadow scores images. Shadow masks were derived with a threshold of 0.1 on the
156 shadow score. For more detailed information on the cloud and shadow masking method see
157 Schmitt *et al.* (2019).

158 The computed masks for TOA images were applied to the BOA collection, and after clouds
159 and cloud shadow masking, S2 BOA images were cropped to the region of interest (Fig. 1),
160 daily mosaicked (merging of same-date tiles) and resampled to 20 m spatial resolution. For
161 each scenario images were filtered according to cloud and shadow mask percent coverage
162 over rice fields. Only those images with at least of 80 % of valid pixels per scenario were
163 included in posterior analysis and, for each valid S2 image (Fig. 3) SI were computed (see
164 section 2.4) and averaged at different scenarios scales.

165

166

167 **Figure 3.** Valid and rejected S2 images

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169 **2.4. Spectral indices**

170 Four SI were calculated according to their utility in estimating rice development, water
 171 management, or production (Table 1). These two and three-band normalized difference
 172 indices are dimensionless, range between -1 and 1, and exploit the VIS, NIR and SWIR
 173 regions of the spectrum (Table 1). The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)
 174 exploits the chlorophyll light absorption in the VIS-red region of the spectrum and the high
 175 reflectance of vegetation in the NIR (Rouse *et al.*, 1974). The Normalized Difference Water
 176 Index proposed by McFeeters (1996), here referred as $NDWI_{MF}$, was developed for
 177 delineating open water bodies by making use of the NIR and VIS-green light. The
 178 Normalized Difference Water Index by Gao (1996), here referred as $NDWI_{GAO}$, was
 179 developed for the remote sensing of vegetation liquid water by using the NIR and SWIR
 180 channels. The Bare Soil Index (BSI) is used to identify bare soil areas and fallow lands, by
 181 combining information from the VIS-blue, VIS-red, NIR and SWIR cannels (Rikimaru *et*
 182 *al.*, 2002).

183

184 **Table 1.** SI used in this study. The $R(\lambda)$ in equations stands for Surface Reflectance at S2 band with
 185 centered wavelength λ in nm*.

Spectral Index	Equation
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Normalized Difference Vegetation Index - NDVI (Rouse et al. 1974)	$\frac{R(842) - R(665)}{R(842) + R(665)}$
Normalized Difference Water Index - NDWI _{GAO} (Gao et al., 1996)	$\frac{R(842) - R(1610)}{R(842) + R(1610)}$
Normalized Difference Water Index - NDWI _{MF} (McFeeters et al., 1996)	$\frac{R(560) - R(842)}{R(560) + R(842)}$
Bare soil index - BSI (Rikimaru et al., 2002)	$\frac{(R(1610) + R(665)) - (R(842) + R(490))}{(R(1610) + R(665)) + (R(842) + R(490))}$

* R(λ) - S2 bands: R(490) - B2, R(560) - B3, R(665) - B4, R(842) - B8, R(1610) - B11 and R(2190) - B12.

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188 2.5. Data smoothing

189 For each S2 valid image and considered scenario, SI data were smoothed with a cubic
190 spline fitting method, thus estimating daily data at different scenario scales, and reducing
191 multi-factorial noise in the original data (*e.g.* atmospheric correction or cloud miss-
192 detection derived errors). Cubic spline fitting is based on the minimization of quadratic
193 errors with curvature type regularization by joining piecewise polynomials smoothly at
194 selected knots from the original data points (Wang, 2011). Thus, the fit is not limited by
195 any method-constrained shape, but phenological shape is driven entirely by the data
196 (Bradley *et al.*, 2007). The cubic spline smoothing was done in R version 3.6 (R CoreTeam,
197 2017) by using the *smooth.spline* function; all data were included as possible knot and the
198 *spar* smoothing parameter was fixed to 0.65.

199

200 **2.6. Rice phenology, hydroperiod and yield**

201 Smoothed SI (NDVI, NDWI_{GAO} and BSI) time series, and their combination, were used to
 202 identify rice phenology, crop evolution, and water management time-series. The presence
 203 of local or critical points in spectral index trends is associated to changes in soil, flooding,
 204 or vegetation stages (Zheng *et al.*, 2016 and Liu *et al.*, 2017). Thus, the first and the second
 205 derivatives were used to identify SI time series maximums and minimums (local points),
 206 and inflection points (critical points). The heading date (HD) is related to the NDVI
 207 maximum (Wang *et al.*, 2014; Tornos *et al.*, 2015; Zhang *et al.*, 2019), and then, other key
 208 features (Table 2) were derived (Fig. 4).

209

210 **Table 2.** Key phenological and field-status features targeted in this study.

Acronym	Key feature	Description
F	Flooding	Management: Flooding of rice fields have started
T	Tillering	Phenology: Active tillering. Number of leaves increases rapidly
HD	Heading Date	Phenology: Vegetative development of rice is maximum
M	Maturity	Phenology and Management: Rice is in mature grain stage and close to be harvested
RF	Re-Flooding	Management: Refers to the optional re-flooding of fields during the fallow season. Implies increase of water level.
EF	End of Flooding	Management: Water in fields is emptied before the land preparation of the next growing cycle
VP	Vegetative Phase	Phenological phase I: From germination to panicle initiation
RP	Reproductive Phase	Phenological phase II: From panicle initiation, till flowering

MRP	Maturity-Ripening Phase	Phenological phase III: From flowering and ripening till M
PF	Permanent Flooding	Management: Period between F and EF. Fields are always flooded but level of water may vary due to punctual drainages.
DLP	Dry Land Preparation	Management: Refers to period during which rice fields are dry and land is being prepared

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212 Selected points were compared to rice calendar in the Ebro Delta (Fig. 2) and validated
 213 with reference data when possible (sowing as the closest ground truth date to NDWI_{GAO}-
 214 derived Flooding and, harvest as the closest date to the derived Maturity date). NDVI was
 215 used to define rice status while NDWI_{GAO} was mainly used to assess water management.
 216 The BSI was used as a complementary index to NDVI and NDWI_{GAO}, and NDWI_{MF} was
 217 used for crop yield estimates. The relationship between annual rice production (kg·ha⁻¹) of
 218 individual rice fields (Scenario ‘D’) and the four SI (Table 1) was assessed with Pearson’s
 219 correlation coefficient (*r*).

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221

222 **Figure 4.** Phenology and irrigation management practices extracted from combined NDVI,
 223 NDWI_{GAO} and BSI. Numbers stand for order of identification of key points. × Inflection
 224 Points ● Local Points. Reference of acronyms is in Table 2.

225 **3. Results**

226 **3.1. Cloud and shadow masking**

227 The adaptation of the cloud and shadow masking method of Schmitt *et al.* (2019)
228 outperformed the default Quality Assessment (QA) band-based cloud mask of S2 L2A
229 imagery (QA60 band) in the Ebro Delta. In the presence of aggregated clouds, the
230 performance of both methods was similar, but in the presence of high and/or disperse
231 clouds and cirrus the QA60 band highly underestimated the cloud-affected coverage
232 compared to the Schmitt method (Fig. 5); QA60 method, overall, underestimated cloud
233 shadows coverage under all conditions. Although the Schmitt method performed better, in
234 some cases it miss-classified pure water (*i.e.* Ebro River and coastal lagoons) as cloud
235 shadows. However, it did not affect the results, since only those pixels within the scenarios
236 defined (Fig.1) were considered. Overall, 53 of 138 images (*ca.* 38.5 %) had more than 20
237 % of pixels affected by clouds or shadows and were discarded; most of them within the
238 period October-December, after the rice growing cycle (Fig. 3).

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Figure 5. The S2 BOA Image clipped to the area of study on 30th July 2019 as viewed in GEE. A) RGB, B) QA60 band-based method, C) Adapted method. White pixels are clouds and shadows. Red squares: Examples of misclassification of water as shadows. (1-column width)

253

254

255 3.2. Spectral indices time-series

256 The cubic spline smoothing filled gaps for fitting time-series with daily information of each

257 spectral index derived from S2 imagery at different scenarios scales. The relationship

258 (Pearson's r and Root Mean Squared Error, RMSE) between observed (satellite-derived)

259 and predicted (smoothing-derived) values, differed among SI. The weaker correlations were

260 for $NDWI_{GAO}$ ($0.77 < r < 0.94$, $0.12 > RMSE > 0.05$), and the strongest correlations were

261 for BSI ($0.84 < r < 0.98$, $0.073 > RMSE > 0.032$), $NDWI_{MF}$ ($0.93 < r < 0.99$, $0.08 > RMSE$

262 > 0.04), and NDVI ($0.95 < r < 0.99$, $0.09 > RMSE > 0.04$). These differences were

263 particularly evident during the rice growing season. At spatial scale, lower number of valid
264 images were obtained for smaller scenarios (*i.e.* individual fields in scenario ‘D’), and at
265 temporal scale, lower number of valid images were available during the post-harvest, in the
266 autumn-winter period (Fig. 3 and Fig. 6), thus affecting the accuracy of the smoothing. To
267 reduce the uncertainty in these extremes of the smoothed time-series, the phenology and
268 hydroperiod phases (see section 3.3) were only classified from the 2018 flooding to the
269 2019 mature-ripening stage, excluding the initial pre-flooding and final post-harvest
270 periods (Fig. 4).

271 SI showed common patterns among the different scenarios considered, and significant
272 differences were not observed among Scenarios ‘A’, ‘B’ and ‘C’. Scenario ‘D’ showed
273 higher variability, mainly due to differences among individual paddy fields, but with
274 common characteristics. In general, both NDVI and NDWI_{GAO} minimum values were
275 observed between the winter till and the middle-spring period (Fig. 6 and 7), coinciding
276 with maximum BSI (Fig. 7). Along the growing season (from May to September), the
277 NDVI and NDWI_{GAO} increased, with a maximum in July-August, with BSI showing an
278 inverse pattern (Fig. 7). The results suggested that the variability of NDWI_{GAO} during this
279 stage was not totally retained by the smoothing (Fig. 6 and 7). In scenario ‘D’, differences
280 among fields were more evident after the growing season (autumn and winter). At this
281 stage, three main SI trends were found: NDVI stabilization with an increase in NDWI_{GAO}
282 and a decrease in BSI; a reduction in both NDVI and NDWI_{GAO} (Field I, Scenario D) with
283 BSI increasing (Fig. 7A); and an increase in both NDVI and NDWI_{GAO} (Field II, Scenario
284 D) associated to a marked a decrease in BSI (Fig. 7B).

285

306 **Figure 6.** Smoothed SI timeseries at different spatial scales. A) NDVI in Scenario ‘A’; B)
 307 NDVI in Field I of Scenario ‘D’; C) NDWI_{GAO} in Scenario ‘A’. Root Mean Squared Error
 308 (RMSE), number of data points (N) and Pearson’s r are provided.

309

310 **3.3. Phenology and hydroperiod detection**

311 Both maximum/minimum and inflection points on NDVI, NDWI_{GAO} and BSI dynamics
312 (Fig. 4) were used to extract phenology and hydroperiod dynamics for the different
313 scenarios considered. Flooding (F), active Tillering (T), Heading Date (HD), Maturity (M),
314 End of Flooding (EF), Vegetative Phase (VP), Reproductive Phase (RP), Mature-Ripening
315 Phase (MRP), Permanent Flooding (PF), Re-Flooding (RF), Dry Land and Land
316 Preparation (DLP) crop phases were identified. Comparing the global trends in 2018 and
317 2019 at different scenarios scales, HD was delayed in 2019 and MRP was shorter in 2019.
318 The temporal variation of NDVI, NDWI_{GAO} and BSI indexes were more related to factors
319 such as water management, type of sowing, field characteristics or climate, than to rice
320 cultivar, see for instance Field II (Fig. 7B), where different rice cultivars were sowed in
321 2018 and 2019. Considering all the fields in scenario 'D', for which reference data was
322 available, rice tillering (T) occurred between 20 and 45 days after sowing in the two years,
323 whereas HD was observed in late July in 2018 and early August in 2019. Maturity (M) was
324 reached 30-50 days after HD, in both years. On average, sowing (ground truth data)
325 occurred 14 ± 5 and 10 ± 4 days after flooding in 2018 and 2019, respectively. Flooding
326 was used for defining the beginning of the vegetative phase (Fig. 4), thus the duration of
327 this phase has probably been overestimated in both years. Rice fields are usually harvested
328 at the end of the maturity stage (harvest maturity), at varying dates depending on farmers'
329 decision (*e.g.* experience, machinery availability, weather). Here, the maturity date derived
330 from NDVI (NDVI maturity) was used as indicator of harvest. According to harvest ground
331 truth data, the average difference between harvest date and NDVI-derived maturity (Fig. 4)
332 was 7 ± 8 days in 2018 and 5 ± 4 days in 2019. In some fields, such as Field II (Fig. 7B), a

333 second NDVI peak was found three months after maturity. Regarding to the hydroperiod
 334 (only defined completely in 2018), fields were flooded in April-May and remained
 335 inundated with different degree of flooding until September – February (depending on the
 336 field), including the re-Flooding phase, which started, when observed, *ca.* 45 days after M
 337 and extended until the beginning of the dry land and dry land preparation phases.

355 **Figure 7.** Rice phenology and hydroperiod at two different sub-scenarios in the Ebro Delta
 356 derived from NDVI, NDWIGAO and BSI timeseries. A) Field I; B) Field II (Fig.1)

357 **3.4. Rice yield estimates**

358 In Scenario ‘D’, SI were correlated (Pearson’s r) with yield production ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$). The
359 strongest correlations were found in the growing season, mainly between July and middle-
360 August (Fig. 8), with rice yield significantly correlated with all SI. The best correlations
361 observed in 2018 and 2019, respectively, were $r = 0.69$ and $r = 0.74$ with NDVI, 0.82 and
362 0.66 with NDWI_{GAO} , -0.84 and -0.86 with NDWI_{MF} , and -0.81 and -0.71 with BSI. Along
363 the summer season, the most consistent relationships with yield production were obtained
364 with NDWI_{MF} and NDVI (Fig. 8).

365 **Figure 8.** Absolute Pearson’s correlation (r) between parcels production ($\text{Kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$) and SI
366 daily values along the period studied.
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369 For this reason, the study focused on the relationships between rice yield and the annual
370 NDVI maximum (at the HD), and the annual NDWI_{MF} minimum (closest local point to

371 HD). Best results (Fig. 9) were obtained when considering only rice fields with mean
372 NDVI > 0.4 ($r = 0.72$) or NDWI_{MF} < -0.4 ($r = -0.80$).

Rice cultivar: ● Bomba ● Carnaroli ● Sirio ● CL111 ● Mare ● Argila ● Okura ● Bahia

373

374 Figure 9. Scatter plot and Pearson's correlation (r) between yearly production by sub-
375 scenario and; A) Maximum yearly NDVI for the corresponding parcels; B) Minimum
376 yearly NDWI_{MF} for the corresponding parcels.

377

378 4. Discussion

379 4.1. Methodological limitations

380 The main limitation were satellite data gaps, since the 40 % of the available S2 images for
381 the selected orbit and period had less than 80 % of valid pixels. The number of rejected

382 images increased in smaller scenarios. Although selection criterion discarded a large
383 number of S2 images, it was necessary for reducing the uncertainty related to cloud and
384 cloud shadow miss-detection and reducing the noise of final mean SI values. Cloud
385 presence and cloud shadow masking is a key issue in optical remote sensing, and the
386 default operational Sentinel-2 QA60 mask systematically underestimate cloud coverage,
387 with higher errors in the presence of thin or patched clouds (Coluzzi *et al.*, 2018). The
388 mean gap between consecutive images was 9 days, usually ranging between 5 (S2 temporal
389 resolution) and 10 days, thus improving other similar platforms such as Landsat, with a best
390 temporal resolution of 16 days. The largest gaps due to cloud presence were of 25 days
391 (November 2019), 30 days (November 2018) and 40 days (December 2019), but in these
392 months a lower variability in rice fields is expected (growing season is from mid-April to
393 early September) and a reduced temporal resolution did not affected the results
394 significantly. Increasing temporal resolution is more important in the growing season when
395 changes occur within days or weeks. In this case, the results evidence the importance of
396 improving the methodology for cloud and cloud shadows detection, mainly in areas with
397 water bodies (*e.g.* river, coastal lagoons), which could led to the overestimation of shadow
398 coverage due to the low reflectance of pure water compared with rice fields (miss-
399 classification of water bodies as cloud shadows).

400

401 **4.2. Application of spectral indices**

402 NDVI, NDWI_{GAO} and BSI were combined to estimate key cropping phases (*i.e.* Flooding,
403 Tillering, Harvest, Maturity and Re-Flooding), and NDWI_{MF} was related to crop yield.
404 NDVI was limited to the rice growing season for assessing rice phenology, mainly
405 Tillering, Heading Date and Maturity. In previous studies, NDVI have been used for

406 showing the transition from bare flooded soil to rice emergence (Tornos *et al.*, 2015). In
407 this study, this transition was not clearly identified since the canopy cover is scarce at the
408 beginning of the cropping and soil-related factors may affect NDVI values (Zhang *et al.*,
409 2019). In relation to the identification of the Tillering stage, the temporal gap between
410 Flooding and Tillering agreed with the common rice farming calendar in the Ebro Delta
411 (Fig. 2). We used the NDVI inflection point before the Heading Date for defining the start
412 of the active Tillering stage as previous works have reported that active Tillering is
413 associated to the maximum increase rate of NDVI associated to the fast growth of rice
414 plants during this stage (Zheng *et al.*, 2016). Heading Date has been related to the
415 maximum in NDVI, which is associated to a peak in Leaf Area Index (LAI), showing an
416 increased in plant biomass (Wang *et al.*, 2014). The maturity date (M) is associated to the
417 initiation of leaf senescence, and hence NDVI is characterized by a fast reduction at the end
418 of this stage (Zheng *et al.*, 2016). The Maturity was significantly related to the harvest date.
419 The delay observed between the maturity date (S2-derived) and the harvest date (reference
420 data) could be related to farmers' harvest practices, since harvest is mediated not only
421 because the ripening state of rice but also considers other external factors (*e.g.* weather,
422 machinery availability).

423 NDWI_{GAO} variations was associated to hydroperiod, and can be applied as an indicator of
424 flooding management in rice paddies (*i.e.* Flooding, End of Flooding and Re-Flooding).
425 Our results were similar to those reported in Tornos *et al.* (2015) in the Ebro Delta and
426 Boschetti *et al.* (2014) in rice fields from Italy, both using data derived from Moderate
427 Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS). NDWI_{GAO} responds to water level
428 fluctuations from flooding to rice tillering, and after rice is harvested. However, with the
429 increase in leaf coverage during the reproductive and rice ripening phases, NDWI_{GAO} could

430 be more associated to the canopy structure, and mediated by plant water content and
431 metabolic activity (Zhang *et al.*, 2019; Serrano *et al.*, 2019). Consequently, NDWI_{GAO} is
432 useful for complementing NDVI-derived phenology and vegetation status during the
433 growing season, but the index variability increased in the presence of vegetation,
434 highlighting the need to improve data frequency.

435 BSI was mainly used for complementing NDVI and NDWI_{GAO} results. Although BSI uses
436 the visible-blue channel (deeper penetration in water), and thus, it may be a better estimator
437 of the beginning of the vegetative phase than the flooding date, its use is not widely
438 extended, probably because the accuracy of visible-blue bands is more influenced by
439 atmospheric conditions. Finally, NDWI_{MF} temporal pattern was similar but inverse to
440 NDVI, thus no additional information on crop cycle was obtained. However, NDWI_{MF} was
441 highly correlated to crop yield in the Ebro Delta. NDWI_{MF} includes the same spectral bands
442 than the Green NDVI (Gitelson *et al.*, 1996) which has been used before for crop yield
443 estimates (Moreno-García *et al.*, 2018). In low-yielding rice system (< 9000 Kg·ha⁻¹), such
444 as the Ebro Delta, two spectral bands SI are not affected by the saturation phenomenon due
445 to low crop biomass (Xue *et al.*, 2014), thus explaining the strong correlation observed
446 between NDWI_{MF} and yield. The best crop yield estimates were obtained with the NDWI_{MF}
447 absolute minimum, suggesting the use of a date close to the HD for accurate estimates.

448 Previous studies have showed that from tillering to harvest, different stages of rice are
449 suitable for crop yield estimation (Xue *et al.*, 2014; Cao *et al.*, 2016; Moreno-García *et al.*,
450 2018), but some of these stages are more complex to identify.

451

452 4.3. Ebro Delta Rice Development (2018-2019) and Management Implications

453 In terms of rice paddies dynamics, similar results were obtained in Scenarios ‘A’, ‘B’, ‘C’,
454 and in most of the fields in Scenario ‘D’, thus showing the homogeneity of agricultural
455 practices in the Ebro Delta along the study period (2018-2019). Those results are similar to
456 those reported by Tornos *et al.* (2015) from 2001 to 2012, which suggested not only spatial,
457 but also temporal homogeneity in rice management in the Ebro Delta. Considering
458 Scenarios ‘A’, ‘B’ and ‘C’, the main differences between both years were related to rice
459 development, such as a delay in heading date and a larger ripening phase in 2019, probably
460 mediated by climatologic factors; for instance, before the start of the growing season the
461 total precipitation in April varied between 40.5 mm in 2018 to 8.9 mm in 2019
462 (Meteorological Service of Catalonia, <https://www.meteo.cat/wpweb/climatologia>).

463 Although different meteorological factors (*e.g.* air, solar radiation) or soil features may
464 affect the crop (Sánchez *et al.*, 2013; Zhao *et al.*, 2016), heavy rains increase field water
465 level, which could contribute to reduce heat and salinity stress to the crop (Martínez-
466 Eixarch *et al.*, 2018), and may modulate the length of the different phenological phases of
467 the crop.

468 At small spatial scales, the use of Sentinel-2 derived SI allowed to capture small dynamics
469 variations among fields (Scenario ‘D’), such as differences in NDVI, NDWI_{GAO} and BSI
470 trends after harvest 2018. These differences were related to different water management
471 practices after harvest. For instance, Field II was Re-Flooded in mid-October 2018, and was
472 not completely dried out until late-January 2019 (Fig. 7B), while Field I was progressively
473 dry out, being partially flooded, but not Re-flooded, until January 2019 (Fig. 7A). Both
474 NDWI_{GAO} and NDVI decreased at the Maturity stage, indicating a reduction in canopy

475 water content at the end of the ripening stage and the drainage of the fields for harvesting.
476 Furthermore, a second NDVI peak was observed in Field II, associated to the Re-Flooding,
477 which may be related to the presence of weed or rice regrowth (Tornos *et al.* 2015).
478 Our study demonstrates the potential of S2-derived SI for the characterization and
479 assessment of the dynamics of rice fields and crop yield estimates in rice farming systems
480 at different spatial scales. The results prove the capability of the combination of different SI
481 for improving the identification of different management practices and rice growth
482 dynamics.

483

484 **5. CONCLUSIONS**

485 Atmospheric conditions (*e.g.* cloud presence) and differences in rice fields characteristics
486 (*e.g.* area, soil properties, management practices) increase the difficulty of using optical
487 remote sensing for the effective monitoring of rice crop. However, the availability of
488 Sentinel-2 satellites from the European Spatial agency, with increased temporal (up to 5
489 days) and spatial (up to 10 m) resolutions, offers new opportunities for many applications.
490 By combining four different S2-derived spectral indexes (NDVI, NDWI_{MF}, NDWI_{GAO} and
491 BSI), key rice farming features were identified (*i.e.* Flooding, Tillering, Heading Date,
492 Maturity, End of Flooding and Re-Flooding after harvest), thus defining the main
493 phenological phases of the crop (*i.e.* Vegetative Phase, Reproductive Phase, Maturity-
494 Ripening Phase), identifying field flooding regimes (flooded or dry), and producing
495 accurate estimates of rice yield at field-scale. Further research must address the
496 increasement of satellite data (*e.g.* fusion of different satellites data, enhanced cloud and
497 shadows masking) and reference data for improving the accuracy of the proposed method

498 on the estimation of rice development and crop yield, and extending the applicability to all
499 the Ebro Delta region and other similar areas (deltaic low-yielding rice systems).

500

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506

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